

Annexe 1: An Examination of Methodological Approaches in Applied Technology Classrooms: A Reflective Perspective from Vocational and Training Educators

Dimensions Information Sheet

These instruments were used to determine methodological considerations regarding digital competence for educators in Vocational Training Applied Technology classrooms (ATC). For this reason, we worked on the items to build different templates: a guided interview for managers, ICT managers, and digital mentors, another for focus groups with teachers from Vocational Training institutes, and an observation guide. The instruments were built from the methodology category's three dimensions (Monitoring, Assessment, and Working Plan).

From this approach, we consider the following areas of knowledge:

Description of the items, dimensions and subdimensions for preparing the template.

Dimension	Subdimensions	Items
Monitoring It refers to how participants been able to carry out the accomplishment and evaluation of the objectives set for the ATC. On the other hand, the level of Teaching Digital Competence has influenced the operation of the AtecA Classroom. (España Consejería de Educación Cultura y Deporte, 2021; López Belmonte et al., 2020; López- Belmonte et al., 2020; Moreno-Guerrero et al., 2021; Sambró et al., 2023; Sanchez-Prieto et al., 2021; Suárez Guerrero et al., 2021).	1.Achievement of Intended Objectives.	item 1: How is the digital project of the centre linked to the ATC Classroom monitored? item 2: In relation to the development of Digital Competence, what benefits does the ATC Classroom provide for students? item 3: In relation to the Digital Centre Project, what aspects do you consider that are not covered by the ATC classroom?
	2.Teaching Digital Competence.	item 4: How are digital technologies promoted from the ATC Classroom? item 5: How are digital technologies promoted from the ATC Classroom? item 6: In terms of monitoring, how are the ATC classrooms aligned with the development of the Digital Competence of students and teachers?
Assesment It refers to how the projects that are linked to the ATC Classroom are evaluated, to know how these projects develop the creativity, innovation and professional activity of VET students. In addition, to know the changes and / methodological adaptations made. (España Consejería de Educación Cultura y Deporte, 2021; Garcia-de-Paz & Santana Bonilla, 2021; Hinojo-Lucena et al., 2020; López- Belmonte et al., 2020; Moreno Guerrero, 2019; Moreno Guerrero et al., 2020; Moreno-Guerrero et al., 2021; Sanchez- Prieto et al., 2021; Suárez Guerrero et al., 2021).	3. Related projects.	item 7: What projects have been developed from the ATC Classroom?
	4.Creativity, innovation, professional activity.	Item 8: How does the ATC Classroom help to promote creativity, innovation and professional activity of VET students? Item 9: How does the ATC Classroom help to improve the social and personal skills of VET students?
	5.Methodological changes.	item 10: Do the activities carried out in the ATC Classroom imply a change in methodological approach that allows promoting student motivation, as they are the main axis of the teaching and learning process?
Working Plan It refers to how the offer of training cycles for professional families has improved. (España Consejería de Educación Cultura y Deporte, 2021; Garcia-de-Paz & Santana Bonilla, 2021; Lorente García, 2014; Sambró et al., 2023; Sanchez-Prieto et al., 2021).	15.Work Environment.	item 11: How does the methodological approach of the ATC Classroom help to meet the needs and expectations of the labour market?

Reference consulted

Year	Document Type	Reference	Source
2021	Institutional Orden 115/2021, de 20 de julio, de la Consejería de Educación, Cultura y Deportes, por la que se crean aulas de tecnología aplicada en determinados centros de titularidad pública de Castilla-La Mancha, que imparten enseñanzas de Formación Profesional 2021/8595]	(España Consejería de Educación de Educación Cultura y Deporte, 2021).	Diario Oficial de Castilla-La Mancha.

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2022	Institutional Instrucciones justificación económica Aulas ATECA 2022.	(España Dirección General de Formación Profesional, 2022).	Dirección General de Formación Profesional, Consejería de Educación, Cultura y Deporte.
2021	Journal Usability and prospective of distance learning in Vocational Training determined by digital competence.	(Moreno-Guerrero et al., 2021).	Revista Aula Abierta.
2021	Journal The transition towards virtual learning environments in a context of health emergency: case study of a teaching team in Initial Vocational Education and Training.	(Garcia-de-Paz & Santana Bonilla, 2021).	RED- Revista de Educación a Distancia.
2020	Journal La Formación Profesional ante el reto de las TIC: Proyección de la realidad aumentada entre su profesorado y predictores de uso.	(López Belmonte et al., 2020).	Revista Complutense de Educación.
2020	Journal Efecto de la competencia digital docente en el uso del blended learning en formación profesional.	(López-Belmonte et al., 2020).	Investigación en bibliotecología: archivonomía, bibliotecología e informática.
2019	Journal Estudio bibliométrico de la producción científica en Web of Science: Formación Profesional y blended learning.	(Moreno Guerrero, 2019).	Píxel-Bit Revista de Medios y Educación.
2014	Journal Perspectivas del profesorado sobre la mejora y potenciación de la formación profesional.	(Lorente García, 2014).	Revista Complutense de Educación.
2021	Journal Aproximación a la competencia digital docente en la formación profesional.	(Suárez Guerrero et al., 2021).	RED- Revista de Educación a Distancia.
2021	Journal Incident Factors in the Sustainable Development of Digital Teaching Competence in Dual Vocational Education and Training Teachers.	(Sanchez-Prieto et al., 2021).	European Journal of Investigation in Health, Psychology and Education.
2021	Journal Competencia Digital Docente del profesorado de FP de Galicia.	(Casal Otero et al., 2021).	Píxel-Bit Revista de Medios y Educación.
2020	Journal B-Learning in Basic Vocational Training Students for the Development of the Module of Applied Sciences I.	(Hinojo-Lucena et al., 2020).	Revista Mathematics.
2020	Journal Gender and Digital Teaching Competence in Dual Vocational Education and Training.	(Sánchez Prieto et al., 2020).	Revista Education Sciences.
2020	Journal Influencia del contexto en el uso de dispositivos TIC en la Formación Profesional Básica.	(Moreno Guerrero et al., 2020).	Revista EDMETIC.
2023	Entrevista Institut de Ciències de l'Educació de la URV.	(Sambró et al., 2023).	Entrevista ICE-URV.

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